

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE
AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

FirmReg Handbook

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1 Introduction

1.1 Aim

The aim of FirmReg is to uniquely identify and integrate the businesses included in the datasets which are part of RISIS.

FirmReg provides an unambiguous list of these firms and attributes them a unique ID which can be used to:

- Match firms between RISIS firm-level datasets (i.e. CIB, Cheetah, VICO).
- Allow the matching of the firms in FirmReg with other datasets within RISIS which contain firm-level data (e.g. patent, publications, trademarks, projects datasets).
- Keep track of linkages between firms in FirmReg (e.g. reflecting the parent/subsidiary structure of the firms included in the register).
- Keep track of the evolution of these firms (e.g. changes in name, location).
- Manage the addition of more firm-level datasets (if necessary).

1.2 Perimeter

Firms are the type of entity covered by FirmReg. The identification of firms (or business enterprises) will follow the same approach adopted by the Frascati Manual, and the System of National Accounts, and will be based on market orientation, i.e. organizations “set up for purposes of engaging in market production”, and “capable of generating a profit or other financial gain for their owners”.

The perimeter of FirmReg includes a *frontend* and a *backend*. The frontend is the main component of FirmReg and includes all the firms belonging to any of the RISIS firm-level dataset. In particular, the frontend of FirmReg includes the firms from the following 3 RISIS firm-level datasets:

- **CIB (Corporate Invention Board)** is a dataset containing the largest and most innovative industrial firms worldwide. CIB combines information extracted from the Industrial R&D Investment Scoreboard (EU Commission), the Orbis financial database and the RISIS Patent database. In particular, CIB includes worldwide firms that fulfilled at least one of these two criteria: 1) High R&D expenditures in the period 2005-2014; 2) More than 10 PCT applications in the period 2005-2014.
- **Cheetah** is a dataset that contains geographical, industry, accounting and ownership information on seven cohorts of medium-sized firms that experienced turnover or employment fast growth rates in the periods 2008-11, 2009-12, 2010-13, 2011-14, 2012-15, 2013-16, and 2014-17. These fast growing medium-sized firms (FGMFs) are located in 30 European countries (EU27, Norway, Switzerland and the UK). Cheetah covers an overall number of 95,407 firms.

- **VICO** is a dataset that contains geographical, industry and accounting information on about 38,000 companies founded starting from 1/1/1988, which have received at least one venture capital or angel investment in the period 1998-2018, operating in the 27 EU countries, United Kingdom and Israel. Moreover, it provides basic information on more than 10,000 distinct investors (e.g. investor type, investor experience, and its geographical location) and investment deals (e.g. deal date, total amount invested in EURO). Last, for each company included in the dataset, VICO also provides information on successful exits (IPO and M&A) and failures.

The backend is an additional section of FirmReg that is provided in order to facilitate the matching of FirmReg with other datasets. It basically includes the subsidiaries of the firms listed in the frontend.

More specifically the inclusion criteria of the subsidiaries depend on the firm-level dataset.

- The majority of CIB firms are Ultimate Owners (i.e. at the top of a corporate ownership structure). Some of them are not Ultimate Owners since they are formally controlled by a holding company, a family, a state. However, in both cases CIB firms are at the top of a corporate ownership structure. In the case of CIB dataset, the backend of FirmReg includes a complete and consolidated list of subsidiaries for all CIB firms (source: ORBIS).
- Not all Cheetah firms are Ultimate Owners. Cheetah datasets includes firms which could be independent companies or subsidiaries of other firms. In other cases, a Cheetah firm may be controlled by another firm, and in turn control other subsidiaries. The backend of FirmReg includes all the subsidiaries for which a Cheetah firm represent an Ultimate Owner (i.e. the top of the corporate ownership structure). If a Cheetah firm is not at the top of a corporate structure, its subsidiaries are not included in the backend of FirmReg.
- VICO firms are generally small entrepreneurial startups at the time of receipt of external financing, and therefore no subsidiaries are included in the backend of FirmReg.

1.3 Firm identifiers

FirmReg assigns to each firm (both frontend and backend firms) a unique identifier (FirmReg ID). Once an ID is assigned to a firm, it will never be reused. If, for any reason, a firm is removed from FirmReg, the corresponding ID will cease to exist, and not be reassigned to a new firm.

FirmReg will retain the same IDs of the prototype version of FirmReg developed during RISIS 1 project. This will allow to identify which firms were also included in the prototype version of FirmReg.

1.4 Structure

FirmReg is composed by five tables: sources, entities, location, names, characteristics, and linkages. The majority of the information necessary to fill in the register tables was already included in the original datasets. The remaining variables were collected from Orbis.

Sources										
FirmReg ID	Fontend vs backend	CIB	Cheetah	VICO	CIB subsidiary	Cheetah subsidiary	BVD ID	CIB ID	Cheetah ID	VICO ID
<i>firmreg_id</i>	<i>frontend</i>	<i>cib</i>	<i>cheetah</i>	<i>vico</i>	<i>cibsub</i>	<i>cheetahsub</i>	<i>bvd_id</i>	<i>cib_id</i>	<i>cheetah_id</i>	<i>vico_id</i>
F_ ISO Country +9digit numeric	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0

Entities							
FirmReg ID	Entity current name	Entity current country	Foundation year	Foundation year remarks	Closure year	Closure remarks	Entity level
<i>firmreg_id</i>	<i>name</i>	<i>country</i>	<i>foundation_year</i>	<i>foundation_remarks</i>	<i>closure_year</i>	<i>closure_remarks</i>	<i>level</i>
F_ ISO Country +9digit numeric	text	ISO country code (2 digits)	year (m=missing)	text	year (m=missing) (a=not applicable)	text	parent; subsidiary (m=missing)

Location								
FirmReg ID	Location ID	Country	City	Postcode	NUTS 3	Location start year	Location end year	Location remarks
<i>firmreg_id</i>	<i>locat_id</i>	<i>country</i>	<i>city</i>	<i>postcode</i>	<i>nuts3</i>	<i>location_start_year</i>	<i>location_end_year</i>	<i>location_remarks</i>
F_ ISO Country +9digit numeric	numeric counter	ISO country code (2 digits)	text	text	text	year (m=missing)	year (a=not applicable); (m=missing)	text

Names						
FirmReg ID	Name ID	Name	Name start year	Name end year	Current name	Name remarks
<i>firmreg_id</i>	<i>name_id</i>	<i>name</i>	<i>name_start_year</i>	<i>name_end_year</i>	<i>current_name</i>	<i>name_remarks</i>
F_ ISO Country +9digit numeric	numeric counter	text	year (m=missing)	year (a=not applicable); (m=missing)	1/0	text

Linkages					
Linkage ID	Parent entity ID	Subsidiary entity ID	Linkage start year	Linkage end year	Linkage remarks
<i>linkage_id</i>	<i>parent_id</i>	<i>subsidiary_id</i>	<i>link_start_year</i>	<i>link_end_year</i>	<i>link_remarks</i>
numeric counter	entity id	entity id	year (m=missing)	year (a=not applicable); (m=missing)	text

2 FirmReg in detail

FirmReg includes 480,296 firms. The firms in the frontend are 136,525, the ones in the backend 343,771. The majority of the firms in the frontend belong to the Cheetah dataset (95,406 firms), followed by VICO firms (38,673) and CIB (3,993). Most of the firms in FirmReg are also matched with Orbis.

Breakdown of FirmReg firms by dataset of origin

Dataset		N	%	Matched with Orbis	Not matched with Orbis
Frontend	CIB	3,993	0.8%	3,991	2
	Cheetah	95,406	19.2%	95,406	0
	VICO	38,673	7.8%	30,038	8637
Backend	CIB subsidiaries	277,698	55.7%	277,698	0
	Cheetah subsidiaries	82,343	16.5%	82,343	0
Total (unduplicated)		480,296	100%	471,659	8,637

Some of the firms in FirmReg belong to more than one dataset. These firms are listed only once and they are identified by a unique FirmReg ID. The total number of firms including the duplicates (firms belonging to more than one dataset) is 498,113.

In particular, among the frontend firms 1,482 firms (about 1.1%) are part of more than one dataset (e.g. a firm is both in CIB and Cheetah databases). If we consider both the frontend and the backend, we have 17,261 firms (about 3.6%) belonging to more than one dataset (e.g. a VICO firm that is also a subsidiary of a CIB firm).

3 Tables description

This section provides a detailed description of each variable included in the 5 tables comprised in FirmReg.

3.1 Sources table

This table contains all the firms in FirmReg (both frontend and backend: 480,296 firms) and links them to their original datasets and with Orbis (if available).

This table includes the following variables:

- **FirmReg ID** (*firmreg_id*): unique identifier of each firm in FirmReg. The IDs have the following format: F_ + ISO Country code + 9 digit numeric counter (e.g. F_FR000000001). The counter starts from 1 for the firms that were included in the first version of FirmReg (e.g. F_DE000000001), while it starts from 100000 for the newly added firms (e.g. F_DE000100001). This will allow to easily identify if a firm was also included in the first version of FirmReg or not.
- **Frontend vs backend** (*frontend*): 0/1 variable indicating if the firm is in the frontend.

- **CIB** (*cib*): 0/1 variable indicating if the firm belongs to CIB dataset.
- **Cheetah** (*cheetah*): 0/1 variable indicating if the firm belongs to Cheetah dataset.
- **VICO** (*vico*): 0/1 variable indicating if the firm belongs to VICO dataset.
- **CIB Subsidiary** (*cibsub*): 0/1 variable indicating if the firm is a subsidiary of a CIB firm.
- **Cheetah Subsidiary** (*cheetahsub*): 0/1 variable indicating if the firm is a subsidiary of a Cheetah firm.
- **BVD ID** (*bvd_id*): Orbis BvD ID (if available).
- **CIB ID** (*cib_id*): CIB dataset internal identifier (for CIB firms only).
- **Cheetah ID** (*cheetah_id*): Cheetah dataset internal identifier (for Cheetah firms only).
- **VICO ID** (*vico_id*): VICO dataset internal identifier (for VICO firms only).

3.2 Entities table

This table includes all the firms in FirmReg (frontend and backend) and contains some of their main demographic details.

This table includes the following variables:

- **FirmReg ID** (*firmreg_id*): firm unique identifier
- **Entity current name** (*name*): current name of the firm. This information is available for all the firms.
- **Entity current country** (*country*): current country in which the firm is located (2 digit ISO country code). This information is available for all the firms in the frontend, and for the vast majority of the firms in the backend. Some subsidiaries in the backend (7,288 firms) do not have the country of origin. In these cases, this variable takes value “ZZ”.
- **Foundation year** (*foundation_year*): foundation year (if available). Missing values are indicated with “m” (Source: Orbis).
- **Foundation remarks** (*foundation_remarks*): notes regarding the foundation year.
- **Closure year** (*closure_year*): Closure year of the firm (if available). The variable takes value “a” (not applicable) if the firm is still in operation, and value “m” if the firm appears to be closed but the year of closure is missing (Source: Orbis).
- **Closure remarks** (*closure_remarks*): this variable takes the following values: “a” (not applicable) if the firm is still active, “m” if the firm is closed but for unknown reason, “bankruptcy”, “dissolved”, “in liquidation”, “inactive” (Source: Orbis).
- **Entity level** (*level*): this variable indicates if the firm is classified as a “parent” company or a “subsidiary” in FirmReg, or whether this information is not available (value “m”). Note: this information reflects the parent/subsidiary status within FirmReg and not necessarily its real ownership status. While firms in the frontend may be classified as parent or subsidiaries, all firms in the backend are classified as subsidiaries

3.3 Location table

This table includes only the firms belonging to the frontend (136,525 firms), and contains information about their location.

The table is designed to accommodate multiple locations for each firm, and to indicate which location is the current one. This version of FirmReg only includes one location for each firm.

This table includes the following variables:

- **FirmReg ID** (*firmreg_id*): firm unique identifier.
- **Location ID** (*location_id*): identifier of the firm location. The IDs have the following format: firmreg_id + 4 digit counter (e.g. F_FR000000001_0001).
- **Country** (*country*): country of location (no missing values).
- **City** (*city*): city of location (if available).
- **Postcode** (*postcode*): postcode of location (if available).
- **NUTS 3** (*nuts3*): NUTS 3 area code (if available).
- **Location start year** (*location_start_year*): the first year since the location is valid, if known (“m” = missing).
- **Location end year** (*location_end_year*): the last year until the location is valid, if known (“m” = missing, “a” = not applicable, i.e. that location is the current one).
- **Location remarks** (*locat_remarks*): Notes regarding location.

3.4 Names table

This table includes all the firms in FirmReg (frontend and backend), and contains information about their names variations.

This information has been retrieved from the original datasets and from Orbis (“also known as” and “previous name” fields). In total this table includes 757,371 name variations.

This table includes the following variables:

- **FirmReg ID** (*firmreg_id*): firm unique identifier
- **Name ID** (*name_id*): identifier of the firm name variation. The IDs have the following format: firmreg_id + 4 digit counter (e.g. F_FR000000001_0001).
- **Name** (*name*): name of the firm
- **Name start year** (*name_start_year*): the first year since the name is valid, if known (“m” = missing).
- **Name end year** (*name_end_year*): the last year until the name is valid, if known (“m” = missing, “a” = not applicable, i.e. that name is the current one).
- **Current name** (*current_name*): 0/1 variable indicating if that name is the current one (the same name is reported in the entities table)

- **Name remarks** (*name_remarks*): Notes regarding name variations. The only note currently available regards VICO firms. Most of these firms are entrepreneurial startups, and many of them end up being acquired by or merged with other firms. Therefore, their current name may be different from the name that these firms had when they were established. In order to facilitate the matching with other dataset, this variable takes value “vico original name” to indicate which specific name variation corresponds to the original name of the startup.

3.5 Linkages table

This table includes all the available parent/subsidiary linkages between firms in FirmReg as described in the introduction section of this document.

This table includes a total of 355,548 linkages between 11,678 parent companies and 355,548 subsidiaries.

This table includes the following variables:

- **Linkage ID** (*linkage_id*): identifier of the linkage (numeric counter).
- **Parent entity ID** (*parent_id*): FirmReg ID of the parent firm.
- **Subsidiary entity ID** (*subsidiary_id*): FirmReg ID of the subsidiary firm.
- **Linkage start year** (*linkage_start_year*): the first year since the linkage is valid, if known (“m” = missing).
- **Linkage end year** (*linkage_end_year*): the last year until the linkage is valid, if known (“m” = missing, “a” = not applicable, i.e. the linkage is still valid).
- **Linkage remarks** (*linkage_remarks*): Notes regarding the linkages.